

A STUDY OF BIOCHEMISTRY PROPERTIES OF POLYGONUM VIVIPARUM L

B. OYUNCHIMEG

Ph.D

Mongolian National University of Medical Sciences, Darkhan- Uul, Mongolia

Abstract. Quantification analyzes such as water, protein, oil, carbohydrate, starch, fiber, sugar, tanning substances, flavonoids, ash, Fe, Zn, Pb, Cd, Ni, amino acid of *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour has been made and calculated calories of powdered *Polygonum viviparum L.* root. Investigated 4 different breads with wheat flour and *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour, 3 different Mongolian traditional cream with *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour and 1 kind of pudding with *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour for the propose of colouring agent. Compared calories of food products with *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour and without *Polygonum viviparum L.* root based on result of biochemistry research and investigation of food products making technology.

Key words: *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour, Polygonaceae, pudding.

1. Introduction *Polygonum viviparum L.* (syn. *Polygonum viviparum*, *Persicaria vivipara*), commonly known as Alpine Bistort, is common all over the high Arctic. It stretches high mountainous areas, along lakes and rivers in meadow soil areas like Khuwsgul, Bulgan, Khenti, Arkhangai, Uwurkhangai and Bayankhongor aimags in Mongolia. It grows to 5-15 cm tall with a thick rootstock. The basal leaves are longish-elliptical with long stalks; upper ones are linear and stalkless. The flowers are white or pink in the upper part of the spike; lower ones are replaced by bulbils. Flowers rarely produce viable seeds and reproduction is normally by the bulbils. Very often a small leaf develops when the bulbil is still attached to the mother plant. The bulbils are rich in starch and are a preferred food for Ptarmigan and Reindeer; they are also occasionally used by Arctic people and nomadic people in Mongolia. Alpine Bistort grows in many different plant communities, very often in abundance.

Figure-1. *Polvaonium viviparum L.*

Polygonum viviparum L. root has been used in the folkloric medicine for treatment of many diseases including gastrointestinal disorders. It has been found to be tonic, styptic and useful in affections of the chest and lungs. It has also been used for the treatments of piles, vomiting, biliousness, chronic bronchitis and wounds. *Polygonum viviparum L.* root has been reported to be astringent and excellent for the treatment of ulcers. Flavonoids like cyanidin, kaempferol, myricetin and quercetin have been reported to be present in leaf. The presense of gallic acid and saponins in rhizomes has been shown.

2. Materials and methods **2.1. Materials** The sample, *Polygonum viviparum L.* root is prepared from Tsagaan burgas region near the Eg Lake in Alag – Erdene sum of Khuwsgul aimag.

2.2. Biochemical methods

In *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour, water analysis was made by mass method in Food research center laboratory of MUST in Darkhan – Uul aimag, ash analysis was made by mass method, minerals analysis was made by Atom Adsorption Spectrophotometer, protein analysis was made by Kjeldal method, oil analysis was made by Soxlet method, sugar analysis was made by Bertran method, starch analysis was made by Everse method, fiber analysis was made by Genberg Gitoman method, tanning substance was made by titration method, amino acid was made by paper chromatograph method, total flavonoids analysis was made by Dowd’s method using spectrophotometer.

2.3. Food products method

Food products with *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour’s physical properties such as colour, odor, taste, reology were identified by sense organs, bread’s acidic was analyzed by Neimon’s method, calories analysis was identified by calculating method in Food research center laboratory of MUST in Darkhan – Uul aimag.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Material’s physical properties

Index	Properties
Colour	Light brown
Odor	Mild, specific
Taste	Tasty, similar nut, very tanning
Texture	Chewable

Because of the colour, *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour was supposed darken the colour of food products. The odor and the taste become better after roasted.

3.2. Biochemical research result

3.2.1. *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour’s biochemical composition

This chart is summarized and compared biochemical composition of medium unriched wheat flour, medium rye unriched flour and *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour.

Index (%)	Wheat flour (medium)	Rye flour (medium)	<i>Polygonum viviparum L.</i> root flour
Water	14.0	14.0	13.0
Oil	1.4	1.5	2
Protein	11.5	9.2	10.85
Carbohydrate	72.5	76	65.6
Starch	69.8	60.4	48.00
Fiber	2.4	14.6	4.7
Sugar	0.3	1.0	12.9
Tannig substance	0	0	1.785
Flavnoids	0	0	0.009

Ash	1.0	1.3	4.9
Fe	0.0009	0.0021	3.6927
Zn	0.0009	0.0020	0.3579
Pb	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0069
Cd	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
Ni	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001

Polygonum viviparum L. root flour's water and protein content was approximate to wheat flour and rye flour. *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour's carbohydrate and starch contents were lesser than the wheat flour and rye flour, but fiber content was double higher than the wheat flour and 3 times lesser than the rye flour and sugar content was 43 times higher than wheat flour and 13 times higher than rye flour. *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour's tanning substance and flavnoids had high values. *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour's ash content was 5 times higher than the wheat flour and 4 times higher than rye flour. It was rich in Fe.

3.2.2. *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour's amino acid composition

There was 15 amino acids (figure-4) in 100 g protein and were compared to wheat flour and rye flour amino acid composition data.

№	Amino acids	Wheat flour (medium)	Rye flour (medium)	<i>Polygonum viviparum L.</i> root flour
1	Cystine+Cystein	2.24	1.97	5.70
2	Lysine*	1.92	3.46	7.33
3	Histidine*	2.12	2.22	3.03
4	Arginine*	3.47	4.52	5.83
5	Aspargin	4.03	6.87	9.52
6	Serine	4.83	5.43	4.88
7	Glycine	3.55	3.81	3.91
8	Glutamine	35.0	27.88	10.82
9	Alanine	3.05	4.13	4.57
10	Threonine*	2.67	3.74	5.66
12	Methionine*	1.75	1.49	3.50
13	Valine	4.18	5.00	7.34
14	Phenilalanine*	4.92	0.50	4.93
15	Leucine*	6.90	6.90	6.68
16	Troptophan	1.61	1.13	0
17	Isoleucine*	3.70	3.85	0
18	Proline	11.74	10.69	0
* - unreplaced amino acids				

There were 8 unreplaced amino acids such as lysine, histidine, arginine, threonine, methionine, phenylalanine and leucine. *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour's lysine, histidine, arginine, threonine, methionine contents are higher than the wheat flour and rye flour. Also cystine, asparagine, tyrosine, valine contents are higher than the heat flour and rye flour. Highest contents of *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour's amino acids are glutamine and asparagine.

Conclusion

1. In *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour, there was water 13%, oil 2%, protein 10.85%, carbohydrate 65%, starch 48%, fiber 4.7%, sugar 12.9%, tanning substance 1.785%, total flavonoids 0.009%, ash 4.9%, Fe 3.6927%, Zn 0.3579%, Pb 0.0069%, Cd less than 0.0001% and Ni less than 0.0001%.

2. *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour's water and protein content was approximate to wheat flour and rye flour. *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour's carbohydrate and contents were lesser than the wheat flour and rye flour, but fiber content was double higher than the wheat flour and 3 times lesser than the rye flour and sugar content was 43 times higher than wheat flour and 13 times higher than rye flour. *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour's tanning substance and flavnoids had high values. *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour's ash content was 5 times higher than the wheat flour and 4 times higher than rye flour. It was rich in Fe.

4. There were 15 amino acids in *Polygonum viviparum L* and there were 8 unreplaced amino acids such as lysine, histidine, arginine, threonine, methionine, phenylalanine and leucine. *Polygonum viviparum L.* root flour's lysine, histidine, arginine, threonine, methionine contents are higher than the wheat flour and rye flour.